

LETTER TO THE NATIONAL INSTITUTES OF HEALTH

Re: RADx-UP Tribal Data Repository

(Notice of Intent to Publish a Funding Opportunity Announcement for RADx Tribal Data Repository
<http://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-22-056.html>)

To the National Institutes of Health:

The Tribal leaders and Indigenous researchers who act as co-signatories to this letter are aware that the NIH's RADx-UP (Rapid Acceleration of COVID-19 Diagnostics for Underserved Populations) project has announced a Request for Applications (RFA) to fund a **Tribal Data Repository** (TDR) to collect, organize, and store data known as Common Data Elements (CDEs) from American Indian and Alaska Native Nations and their citizens. The anticipated \$12 million award would be presented to an organization that supports investigators with a documented history of Tribal partnership, research in biomedical sciences and/or social determinants of health research and/or resilience, data governance, biobanking, epidemiological tracking and data aggregation, machine learning and artificial intelligence, and a record of supporting Tribal sovereignty.

We understand and support the role of science and research in promoting healthy American Indian and Alaska Native communities. Indeed, we, as Indigenous advocates, actively work at the intersection of research and public health to improve the quality of health, economy, and culture for our American Indian and Alaska Native peoples, often using Federal funds and mechanisms to enable this work.

We acknowledge and appreciate increased attention by the NIH toward respecting Tribal sovereignty and Tribal data ownership. However, we caution that this repository, as worded in the Notice of Intent for the RFA, centers NIH contexts for its form and function. This model may be perceived as continued extraction as data is moved to sites lacking Tribal regulations or oversight. We think that data should be under complete governance of Tribes, as the RFA itself supports. However, the NOI contradictorily states:

- 1) "The RADx TDR is intended to be an independent, Tribally directed research data repository using a sovereignty-based governance structure that will provide responsible data sharing and access to researchers and their collaborators who are generating or interested in working with RADx AI/AN research data."
- 2) "RADx funded projects are required to collect all NIH RADx Required Common Data Elements and share these data at a cadence defined by NIH and Tribal Nation data transfer and use agreements throughout the life of the project."

That the NIH wishes to define the CDEs and the cadence of dissemination is antithetical to a repository with sovereignly controlled Tribal governance. **If the NIH truly wishes to promote Tribal self-determination, then it naturally follows to grant Tribal Nations the sole authority and agency to grow and strengthen their own Tribal data ecosystems, governance structures, resource controls, and data economies in a way that suits their own needs, supported but not defined by the NIH.**

Without rigorous attention to Tribal asset development, legal precedents, and full Tribal governance, the planned TDR risks recapitulating negative histories at a time when the benefits and consequences of Big Data could not be higher. For example, Tribal representatives recently sued the US government

(Cobell vs Salazar) for overexerting Federal authority on Tribal resources. To avoid the recurrence of similar scenarios, data from Tribes should be managed by Tribes. Throughout the pandemic, many of us have had concerns of non-Tribal regulatory frameworks such as HIPAA, Public Health Law, the Common Rule, and FDA taking precedence over Tribal regulatory frameworks. We acknowledge the short-term urgency of the pandemic, but any long-term data infrastructure plan by the NIH should not take precedence over Tribal sovereignty or proper Nation-to-Nation processes. To instantiate an entity that may be difficult to dislodge through slow bureaucratic correction is extremely dangerous to Tribal sovereignty. Below are specific comments and concerns along with suggestions for moving forward, *if Tribes want to move forward with an NIH Tribal Data Repository*:

1. **Transparency, Accountability, and Limits to NIH Authority in Tribal Domains.** We recognize that the planned TDR has far-reaching intellectual property, economic, and policy implications between the Federal government and Tribal Nations. While current plans restrict this NIH-centered repository to CDE data, Tribes must be given full and transparent assurance of the limited scope and mission of the Repository. This plan should include clear expiration dates for archival data and a detailed plan for the return of data at the end of the pandemic or whenever COVID-19 no longer constitutes a public health emergency.
2. **Process.** We think that the timeline for Tribal consultation for such an RFA must be extended with more rigor and transparency. These consultations should include explicit discussions of clearly defined data collection boundaries and endpoints, mission creep restrictions, and safeguards to political manipulation. This effort cannot be said to be “for Tribes” if the endeavor has not adequately sought input from the 10-15 Federally recognized Tribal Nations who are participating, in varied contexts, with the COVID-19 RADx-UP program, especially since this group constitutes a minute fraction of the total 574 Federally recognized Tribal Nations.
3. **Utility.** As currently used CDEs vary between Tribes, the utility of the Repository as an analytical hub for COVID relief may be futile as harmonization across datasets with dissimilar data types renders the resource less useful. Furthermore, without open dialogue, the TDR may be perceived as an opening for Federal stakeholders to begin rulemaking without prior consultation and consent to ensure equal decision-making authority by Tribes. Any Repository should be created with laws and policies that allow Tribes to manage and recall data regardless of changes in Federal administration and subsequent changes in attitudes toward Tribal control.
4. **Freedom to Negotiate.** Federal accounting processes often conflict with US-Tribal negotiations with regard to public sentiments on tax spending and sanctions against *perceived* race-based preference. Though NIH expenditures are accountable to Congress, these same expectations are not the same for Tribes as Tribal-Federal relations are negotiated differently. Failure to engage Tribes as treaty entities creates a power imbalance that simultaneously dismisses the primacy of treaty rights and law. Tribes must be able to own, manage, and keep private their own data without being subject to Federal policy mandates. To ensure equitable negotiations, additional Indigenous expert voices (academics, scientists, ethicists, sociologists) need to be granted agency to consult with Tribally elected officials prior to discussion with NIH project leaders.
5. **Preferred Model and Process.** Although the curation, centralization, and harmonization of Big Data is the default strategy championed by many in the fields, we believe that Indigenous ontologies, etymologies, and axiologies are fundamentally different from the majority population.

We suggest a decentralized repository model that considers Tribal commonalities by geography, culture, local and Federal financial resources, and health concerns. This self-organizing system of Tribal repositories would provide better governance logistics and more contextually tailored analyses and mitigation strategies. To fulfill the Federal government's trust responsibility and treaty obligations, such a model should include:

- a. Adherence to the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, which provides high-level, minimum expectations for the stewardship of Indigenous data. The CARE Principles do not supersede individual Tribal Nations' protocols, rather they support those rights, interests, and expectations at scale and serve to protect Tribal citizens' and other Indigenous people's data within non-Tribal contexts, such as research studies in urban areas, public health surveillance data, and repositories.
- b. Contracts that are robust with respect to corporate and/or treaty law with individual Tribes as signatories (DUAs, MOUs or MOAs have been shown to be woefully insufficient in respect to Tribal data surveillance and accountability).
- c. Binding agreements that ensure immediate and total data erasure or Tribal transfer in the event of a Tribe's or community's withdrawal from the Repository.
- d. Increased capacity and training to support local Tribal interventions and strategies to implement long-term Tribally governed data sharing.
- e. Aid from the NIH to petition for separate and additional funding venues to support American Indian/Alaska Native research.
- f. A threshold of Tribal benefit must be decided by Indigenous peoples *before* extending access to outside researchers, if Repository use by non-Indigenous persons is a goal.

Sentiments that support these recommendations were similarly delivered to the NIH by the National Congress of American Indians ([https://www.ncai.org/policy-research-center/research-data/recommendations/NCAI Letter NIH COVID19 Research 6 5 2020 FINAL signed.pdf](https://www.ncai.org/policy-research-center/research-data/recommendations/NCAI_Letter_NIH_COVID19_Research_6_5_2020_FINAL_signed.pdf)):

“[C]ollection and storage of data and specimens [. . .] and any plans for data management and sharing, must follow Tribal research laws and policies. Every Tribal Nation, as a sovereign Nation, has the inherent right to determine how research is governed when it involves their citizens and lands even if they do not have specific research laws in place.”

To truly serve Indigenous people through these efforts, it is not merely enough to follow the “letter of the law” when consulting and engaging data policies with Tribes. Many Tribal Nations do not yet have written Tribal laws or legal resolutions of their own in place that adequately address the complexities of Tribal data management.

Overall, we feel consultation for this RFA could have been strengthened and would like to see consultation processes continue. Notification letters should not serve as proxy to consultation as they often fail to identify key personnel within Tribal governments and lack verified response. Response letters should be answered by a designated Tribal employee via US certified mail. Consultation should adhere to Indigenous Data Sovereignty standards and ensure Tribes are fully informed to make their decisions.

When this RFA is awarded, our recommendation and hope is that it does not simply fund the creation of a Repository and associated physical structures but has complimentary roles in creating equitable consultation frameworks with Tribes. Careful monitoring and iterative reframing of the Repository is an absolute necessity if it is to be successful and accountable to Tribal interests. Most importantly, we

hope that this RFA not only acknowledges Tribal sovereignty but makes an unprecedented move towards uplifting Tribally managed data ownership.

Sincerely,

Native Academics and Tribal leaders